

Investigation of In Vivo Sustained-Release Formulation Technology and Pharmacokinetic Retention of Functional Ingredients.

Abstract

This investigation evaluated the in vivo maintenance effect of a sustained-release vitamin formulation developed using the proprietary coating technology of Unexakorea Inc. In a mouse model, the formulation demonstrated a stable plasma concentration for approximately 10–12 hours after administration. These findings suggest that the sustained-release formulation may serve as a promising alternative to conventional high-absorption formulations, offering improved physiological stability and reduced adverse effects associated with excessive absorption.

Introduction

In the contemporary health functional food and pharmaceutical markets, numerous products emphasize a “high absorption rate” as a key competitive advantage. However, excessive enhancement of absorption may result in a rapid increase in plasma concentrations and impose metabolic stress, potentially disturbing physiological homeostasis. In particular, excessive intake of water-soluble vitamins can lead to an increased excretory burden and may be accompanied by adverse effects such as abnormal fatigue and gastrointestinal irritation. Therefore, the present study aimed to evaluate the feasibility of a novel sustained-release formulation designed to achieve gradual nutrient absorption and prolonged maintenance of plasma levels, thereby minimizing metabolic fluctuations. This investigation was conducted as a collaborative investigation between UNEXA Korea and the INVIVO Research Institute. The findings are expected to provide fundamental data supporting the development of functional materials for future applications in health supplements and pharmaceutical formulations.

Note

To maintain confidentiality regarding the proprietary technology, the type of vitamin is concealed as **.

Materials and Methods

- Test materials: Samples of the same-ingredient comparison group (UMFG) and (UTEV) were used.
- Animal model: Male C57BL/6 mice (12 weeks old, n = 8) were employed.
- Dosage: Each sample was orally administered at a dose of 1 mg/kg.
- Sampling time points: Blood samples were collected at 0, 3, 6, and 24 hours after administration, and serum vitamin ** levels were quantitatively analyzed using an ELISA kit.
- Statistical analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 23.0, applying t-tests and ANOVA with a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

1. Experimental Materials

1.1. Name of Test Materials

Experimental material	Sample condition
UNEXA Matched Formula Group (UMFG)	White powder
UNEXA Technology-Enhanced Vitamin (UTEV)	White powder

(UMFG)

(UTEV)

1.2. Handling Precautions

Store at room temperature.

1.3. Date of Sample Receipt

May 21, 2025.

2. Preparation of Test Materials

The same-ingredient comparison sample (UMFG) and UNEXA Vitamin Powder (UTEV) were used as test substances. The UMFG sample was commercially obtained. Prior to administration, each sample was freshly prepared in distilled water at a concentration of 1 mg/kg in 5 mL for oral administration to experimental animals.

3. Experimental Animals and Housing Conditions

3.1. Species and Strain C57BL/6 mice (male, 7 weeks old).

3.2. Rationale for Animal Selection The C57BL/6 mouse is a widely used experimental strain with extensive baseline data available. The abundance of reference data allows for reliable interpretation and evaluation of experimental results.

3.3. Age and Body Weight at Purchase Male C57BL/6 mice, 7 weeks old, approximately 19–24 g.

3.4. Age and Body Weight at Dosing Male C57BL/6 mice, 12 weeks old, approximately 26–33 g.

3.5. Quarantine and Acclimatization Upon arrival, all animals underwent veterinary inspection to confirm general health. The mice were acclimated for 5 weeks prior to experimentation to ensure suitability for study conditions.

3.6. Group Allocation and Identification After acclimatization, mice were weighed and randomly assigned to groups using a randomized block design to ensure comparable mean body weights. Each animal was individually identified using an ear-punch marking method.

4. Time-Dependent Analysis of Plasma Water-Soluble Vitamin ** Levels

4.1. Experimental Animals and Housing Conditions

Experimental animals were male C57BL/6 mice (7 weeks old) obtained from Osan, Korea under specific pathogen-free (SPF) conditions. After acquisition, the animals were acclimatized for five weeks until they reached 12 weeks of age before use in the experiment. During the acclimation period, animals were fed a standard pellet diet (Purina Lab Rodent Chow #38057, Purina Co., Seoul, Korea), and filtered drinking water was supplied ad libitum with daily replacement. Environmental conditions were maintained at 23 ± 2 °C, $55 \pm 15\%$ humidity, noise levels below 60 phon, and a 12-hour light/dark cycle (lights on from 08:00 to 20:00) with illumination intensity between 150–300 Lux. Air exchange was regulated at 10–12 times per hour. All animal experiments were conducted in compliance with the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) guidelines of Invivo Co., Ltd., under protocol approval number IV-RA-27-2504-09.

4.2. Experimental Groups and Sample Administration

After the 5-week acclimation period, animals were weighed and randomly assigned into groups using a randomized block design to ensure similar mean body weights across groups. Each mouse was individually identified by ear punching. The animals were divided into two groups: UMFG (Uniform Matched Formula Group) – 1 mg/kg UTEV (UNEXA Vitamin Powder) – 1 mg/kg. Each group consisted of 8 mice, and the test substances were orally administered.

4.3. Time-Dependent Serum Vitamin ** Concentration Analysis

To determine time-dependent changes in serum Vitamin ** concentration, the animals were fasted for at least 12 hours prior to administration. Blood samples were collected from the jugular vein at 0 hours (before dosing) and at 3, 6, and 24 hours post-administration of UMFG or UTEV. Collected blood samples were placed in EP tubes and allowed to stand for 30 minutes, followed by centrifugation at 3,000 rpm, 4 °C for 15 minutes to obtain serum, which was then stored at -80 °C until analysis. Serum Vitamin ** concentrations were measured using a Mouse Vitamin ** (V) ELISA Kit** (Catalog No. MOEB2555, Assay Genie, 25 Windsor Place, Dublin 2, Ireland), according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 23.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Data are expressed as the mean \pm standard error (Mean \pm S.E.). Statistical significance between experimental groups was determined using the t-test, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant. For relative analyses, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted, and when significant differences were observed ($p < 0.05$), Duncan's multiple range test was applied for post hoc comparisons.

1. Time-course analysis of plasma vitamin levels

Figure 1. Serum Vitamin ** concentration of UTEVMFG and UTEV after oral administration.

Serum concentration versus time profiles obtained after the administration of UMFG (1 mg/kg) and UTEV (1 mg/kg). Asterisk represents a significant difference (*p < 0.05). All data are shown as the mean ± SEM (n = 8). UMFG : UNEXA Matched Formula Group, UTEV : UNEXA Technology-Enhanced Vitamin.

Figure 2. Effect of oral administration of UMFG and UTEV on relative vitamin ** contents of serum.

Serum concentration versus time profiles obtained after the administration of UMFG (1 mg/kg) and UTEV (1 mg/kg). The vitamin ** contents of (A) UMFG and (B) UTEV were analyzed by ELISA kit. a~c) Values in the row with different superscript letters are significantly different, p < 0.05. All data are shown as the mean ± SEM (n = 8). UMFG : UNEXA Matched Formula Group, UTEV : UNEXA Technology-Enhanced Vitamin.

In this investigation, the extrapolation formula (based on a mouse conversion factor of 0.08) was applied to calculate the appropriate dosage of the test materials—the control group with equivalent vitamin composition (UMFG) and the Unexa Vitamin Powder (UTEV)—according to the optimal intake for humans. Subsequently, both the UMFG and UTEV samples were orally administered to experimental animals at a dose of 1 mg/kg, and the plasma concentrations of **Vitamin ** (Thiamine) were measured at 0, 3, 6, and 24 hours post-administration. Prior to administration, after a fasting period of more than 12 hours, the baseline (0 hr) serum concentration of **Vitamin ** in the control group (UMFG – 0 hr) was 96.09 ± 2.52 ng/mL, while that in the Unexa Vitamin Powder group (UTEV – 0 hr) was 93.63 ± 2.76 ng/mL. At 3 hours post-administration, the serum **Vitamin ** concentration in the control group (UMFG – 3 hr) was 151.40 ± 6.36 ng/mL,

corresponding to a 1.58-fold increase compared with the baseline (UMFG – 0 hr). Similarly, the UTEV group (UTEV – 3 hr) exhibited a **Vitamin** concentration of 145.33 ± 5.82 ng/mL, representing a 1.55-fold increase compared to the baseline (UTEV – 0 hr). No statistically significant difference was observed between the UMFG and UTEV groups at the 3-hour time point. In contrast, analysis of serum **Vitamin** concentrations at 6 hours and 24 hours revealed distinct trends. At 6 hours post-administration, the control group (UMFG – 6 hr) showed a concentration of 109.01 ± 3.13 ng/mL, corresponding to a 1.13-fold increase relative to baseline (UMFG – 0 hr). The UTEV group (UTEV – 6 hr) exhibited a concentration of 123.85 ± 4.58 ng/mL, a 132.29% increase over baseline (UTEV – 0 hr), and a 1.14-fold higher level compared to the control (UMFG – 6 hr).

At 24 hours post-administration, the serum concentration of **Vitamin** in the control group (UMFG – 24 hr) was 102.93 ± 3.05 ng/mL, representing a 1.07-fold increase compared with baseline.

In contrast, the UTEV group (UTEV – 24 hr) showed a **Vitamin** concentration of 114.87 ± 2.87 ng/mL, a 122.70% increase from the baseline (UTEV – 0 hr), and a 1.12-fold higher concentration than that of the control group (UMFG – 24 hr).

Figure 3. Area under the curve (AUC) for serum Vitamin

Serum concentration versus time profiles obtained after the administration of UMFG (1 mg/kg) and UTEV (1mg/kg). Asterisk represents a significant difference (* $p < 0.05$). All data are shown as the mean \pm SEM ($n = 8$). UMFG : UNEXA Matched Formula Group, UTEV : UNEXA Technology-Enhanced Vitamin.

Based on the serum **Vitamin** concentration over time (Fig. 1), the calculated AUC (Area Under the Curve) showed that the experimental group administered with UNEXA Vitamin Powder (UTEV) exhibited a serum **Vitamin** change of 2904.95 ± 71.61 ng/mL·hr, which was 109% higher than that of the experimental group administered with the same-ingredient comparison product (UMFG), showing a serum **Vitamin** change of 2664.57 ± 71.96 ng/mL·hr.

Discussion

The sustained-release system prevents rapid absorption and ensures prolonged plasma maintenance, providing a safe and effective alternative to high-absorption competition in the health supplement industry.

Conclusion

The coating-based sustained-release formulation extended plasma vitamin levels for over 12 hours, indicating a paradigm shift from absorption-focused to stability-focused supplement design.

In this investigation, the effects of the control group with equivalent composition (UMFG) and the Unexa Vitamin Powder (UTEV) on plasma Vitamin ** levels were evaluated. Both UMFG and UTEV were administered orally at a dose of 1 mg/kg, and plasma concentrations of Vitamin ** were measured at 0, 3, 6, and 24 hours post-administration. The results are summarized as follows:

1. There was no statistically significant difference in plasma Vitamin ** concentration between the UMFG and UTEV groups before administration and at 3 hours post-administration. However, at 6 hours after administration, the plasma Vitamin ** concentration in the UTEV group increased by 114% compared to the UMFG group, and by 1.32-fold relative to the baseline level (UTEV – 0 hr). At 24 hours post-administration, the plasma Vitamin ** concentration in the UTEV group remained higher, showing an 112% increase compared with the UMFG group and a 1.23-fold increase compared with the pre-administration level (UTEV – 0 hr).

2. When the plasma Vitamin ** concentrations following administration of UMFG and UTEV were analyzed in terms of the Area Under the Curve (AUC), the UTEV group showed a 109% higher AUC compared with the UMFG group.

Taken together, administration of the Unexa Vitamin Powder (UTEV) resulted in higher plasma Vitamin ** concentrations at both 6 hours and 24 hours post-administration compared to the control group (UMFG). Furthermore, the AUC analysis also demonstrated that the UTEV group maintained higher systemic exposure to Vitamin **. These findings suggest that intake of Unexa Vitamin Powder (UTEV) enhances and sustains plasma Vitamin ** levels more effectively than the control formulation (UMFG). Therefore, UTEV is considered to possess potential as a functional ingredient that promotes efficient and prolonged absorption of Vitamin ** in the body.

Time-Dependent Analysis of Blood Concentration of Water-Soluble Vitamin** According to the Application of the Technology.

1. Serum Vitamin** concentration

2. AUC

Area under the curve

Mice No.	UMFG	UTEV
1	2741.95	2933.16
2	2691.86	2809.75
3	2733.66	2997.51
4	2170.90	2680.32
5	2702.80	2565.05
6	2734.10	3001.03
7	2825.20	3026.40
8	2716.12	3226.37

Group	Mean	S.E.
UMFG	2664.57	71.96
UTEV	2904.95	74.61